

Space-Dependent Potential and Interaction Through Quantum Resonances?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 13, 2023

In Newtonian mechanics, a space-dependent potential $V(x)$ is associated with both a change in energy in x and a conservative force $-dV/dx$. There is no notion of an interaction through a resonance, even though classically resonance situations exist.

A quantum free particle is represented by the space and time two-dimensional probability distributions $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ with x and t representing independent variables, even though on average there exists the relationship $x = p/m t$. In the case of the time-independent Schrodinger equation, one uses a potential $V(x)$ taken from "classical" physics which is combined with the nonclassical $\exp(ipx)$ (i.e. with time removed). An immediate issue, we argue, is that $V(x)$ implies different potential energy values at each x , while $\exp(ipx) \rightarrow \cos(px)$ describes probabilities at different x points associated with the same p . According to classical mechanics, p should change from one x point to another in a deterministic manner governed by $V(x)$. Thus there exists a contradiction.

We argue that the probabilistic form $\cos(px)$ remains intact, but that the interaction between an $\exp(ipx)$ and $V(x)$ involves the formation of a probability resonance which involves other $\exp(ipx)$ s in the problem. In other words, $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ suggests that the potential also behaves in a probabilistic manner and one may have $V_k \exp(ikx) a(p-k) \exp(i(p-k)x) = V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx)$.

One may argue that $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ is simply a mathematical formalism (namely a Fourier series) without any physical manifestation. In this note, however, we argue against this and suggest that the "resonance" involved is linked with physical probability distributions which exist in both $V(x)$ and external energy-supplying objects (such as a photon). According to the time-independent Schrodinger equation there are discrete energy levels associated with this differential equation, so an entity which may provide energy is required to lift a quantum bound particle from one energy level to the next. Electrons in an atom absorb photons to move to higher levels. Thus the photon is an energy-supplier and the fact that it has a spatial wavelength does not seem to directly enter into the solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. If, however, a particle may only interact through a probability resonance, we argue that it is not only the potential $V(x)$ which must physically be able to interact in a probabilistic way, but also any energy entities used to supply energy. Thus we argue that a photon must have a spatial distribution i.e wavelength to allow it to be part of the formation of spatial resonances in the particle - $V(x)$ system which it in fact does. Thus we argue that the wavelength of a photon is experimental evidence for x -probability distribution resonances which occur between $V(x)$ and a bound particle.

Information and Space-Time Features of a Quantum Particle - $V(x)$ Interaction

In a previous note (1), we argued that a quantum free particle $\exp(ipx) \exp(-iEt)$ is somewhat invariant (periodic) in both space and time with the two variables x, t being independent, but an average relationship $x = p/m t$ existing. $\exp(ipx)$ is the eigenfunction of $-i^*$ the spatial translational generator d/dx and $\exp(-iEt)$ the eigenfunction of i^* the time translational generator d/dt .

In (1) we argued that from an information point of view and equilibrium that when a spatial potential $V(x)$ is introduced, the system will try to recreate a kind of spatial invariance through $KE_{ave}(x) = V(x) = E$. This is exactly the same situation as in Newtonian mechanics. Here we wish to look at the situation in a slightly different way.

$V(x)$ is a function of x which combines with $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, but where are the $\exp(-iEt)$ pieces? Why cannot one create: $\sum_p b(p)\exp(-i E(p) t)$? If this latter superposition holds, one would argue that there needs to exist a function $B(t)$ (analogous to $V(x)$) which allows for the various $\exp(-i E(p) t)$ s. For example, a quantum free particle $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$ does not spontaneously become a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ states etc. No $B(t)$ function, however, seems to exist in the problem. From an information point of view, if energy is associated with time and one only has $V(x)$, one should consider the distribution $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ such that the $a(p)$'s yield a constant energy E at each x . This single energy may then be associated with $\exp(-iEt)$

One may alternatively argue that given $V(x)$ one retains the conservation of energy form of classical mechanics i.e. $KE(x)+V(x) = E$. Given $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ one would then simply try to create a conservation of energy equation. In classical mechanics, however, there is no $\exp(-iEt)$ function, but one is still describing the bound isolated system as one which does not change in time in a particular way. Certainly p, v and $pp/2m$ change in time, but there is a piece of information, namely total E which does not.

Wavelength and Contradiction with $V(x)$

$V(x)$ represents a Newtonian conservative potential which changes at each x point, indicating a change of energy at each point. This, however, completely contradicts the notion of $\exp(ipx)$ which contains two x -probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which have wavelength = \hbar/p ranges. Thus there is no change in kinetic energy or any other energy within this range if $\exp(ipx)$ is to be taken seriously. Why should $\exp(ipx)$ be taken seriously within a single particle quantum bound system when it only represents a free particle? We argue that a bound particle may be knocked out of the bound system becoming a free particle represented by $\exp(ipx)$. In previous notes we argued that the "information" of the free particle cannot be lost within a bound state. In this note, we argue that this information is really associated with the type of interaction which occurs. We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ representing two x -probability distributions means that a certain type of probability interaction/resonance occurs in nature as exhibited by the two slit experiment. (In such a case, the particle interacts with the two-slit system.)

Thus we argue that $\exp(ipx)$ s must interact in a probabilistic manner within a bound system $V(x)$. This means that $V(x)$ changes from one x to another in an average manner in the same way that $x=p/m t$ is an average description. Specifically, $V(x)$ must have the ability to interact through x -probabilities as well. In (2) we argue that the probability distribution $\exp(ipx)$ carries the information of the impulse which created p . Thus a high p is linked with a small wavelength \hbar/p or sharp hit in space. The length of the hit in space i.e. the wavelength is associated with the probability distribution $\cos(px)$. We argue that a kind of probability resonance occurs during impulse hits of the form:

$$\exp(ikx) \exp(i(p-k)x) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

As a result, a potential physically interacts with various $\exp(ipx)$ s in a resonance type manner. In particular, one takes the time-independent Schrodinger equation and writes $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and collects the coefficients of a particular $\exp(ipx)$:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2 p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = E_n \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

This we argue shows the probability resonances between $V(x)$ i.e. $\exp(ikx)$ and the various $\exp(ipx)$ s.

One may argue that ((2)) is merely a formalism and does not physically prove a potential interacts physically through an x-probability resonance scheme (where we call ((1)) the form of a resonance). We note that for the free particle $\exp(ipx)$, this form is not a mathematical contrivance as it is physically borne out through a two slit experiment, but in ((2)) we have given no experimental evidence for $V(x)$ having the form $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. After all, this is only a mathematical Fourier series and not necessarily a physical statement. In the next section, however, we try to argue that interactions are physically of the x-probability resonance type.

Photon Absorption and Emission from an Atom

In the above section, we argued that a particle may be knocked out of a quantum single-particle bound state and is then represented by $\exp(ipx)$. In the case of an atom, however, one may have a third entity namely a photon and we try to use this to argue for the existence of a physical x-probability resonance.

If one solves the time-independent Schrodinger equation: $-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} / W + V(x) = E_n$, one finds discrete energy values E_n . Thus, an amount of energy of $E_{n2} - E_{n1}$ is needed to knock an electron from level $n1$ to $n2$. $E_{n2} - E_{n1}$ is simply an energy amount, it does not indicate that an x-probability resonance occurs. Experimentally, a photon may supply this energy and also be emitted when a particle drops from E_{n2} to E_{n1} . The photon happens to have a wavelength as may be measured in a two slit experiment. In general, the requirement of an energy source does not prove that wavelength is needed for the problem, but we argue that the photon wavelength is not an extra piece of information. Rather we argue that the presence of the photon wavelength i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ structure is experimental evidence that a piece of energy which interacts (which is also what $V(x)$ is) has the x-probability structure needed to create a resonance form. Thus we argue that a potential does not simply represent a change of energy with x , but is linked with an x-probability resonance as the form of interaction. This bypasses the contradiction of having an $\exp(ipx)$ with a probability to be within a wavelength \hbar/p and not have a change in potential energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the form $\exp(ipx)$ of a free quantum particle suggests it has probabilistic x distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. Thus one cannot deterministically predict its motion within a wavelength, although on average it moves with $x=p/m t$. In (2) we argue that this probability distribution stores the physical information of the impulse used to create p in the first place. Thus it has a physical origin.

The x probability distribution poses a problem if one introduces the classical potential $V(x)$ which states that energy and hence p should change at each x . A given p does not change within a wavelength. We argue that one way to avoid this contradiction is to suggest that x -probability distribution resonances are the physical manner in which quantum interactions occur. In other words, one uses $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$. This, however, is only a mathematical statement, namely a Fourier series and does not prove that such resonances physically exist. We argue, however, that the fact that a photon is absorbed by an atom to push an electron to a higher energy level indicates that an energy supplying object (the photon) also has an x -probability distribution i.e. a wavelength and is described by $\exp(ip_1 x)$. Thus the photon does not simply supply energy as one may think by only looking at the time-independent Schrodinger equation (which does not include the photon), but creates an x -probability resonance due to its wavelength. Thus we suggest that $V(x)$ should physically form an x -probability resonance in the same manner.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Newton's Second Law in Terms of Information (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Free Particle and Internal Force (preprint, zenodo, 2023)